

A report to inform the decision whether fast food outlets should
be banned near schools

(ES30083: Coursework)

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Obesity is an increasingly widespread problem for children in the UK, making them more likely to miss school and suffer from serious health conditions. A growing body of literature identifies the influence of obesogenic environments, specifically fast food outlets (FFOs), on childhood obesity (PHE, 2014). Over 50% of local authorities (LAs) in England now have planning guidance in place to promote a healthy food environment (Keeble et al., 2019) and a number of councils are limiting children’s access to FFOs by implementing exclusion areas near schools.

Childhood obesity is near historic highs, affecting one-fifth of Y6 children and one-tenth of Reception children. It is twice as prevalent for those living in the most versus the least deprived areas (NHS, 2023), impacting future health and labour market outcomes (Cawley, 2015), exacerbating inequalities. Increases in fast food consumption, long associated with weight gain (Pereira et al., 2005) and driven by the proliferation of fast food outlets (FFOs) (BBC, 2018) and families eating out more, have been touted as important factors in explaining recent obesity trends. In the academic literature, the relationship between increases in FF supply and childhood obesity is well established, but many of these studies, detailed in Table 1, are limited in their explanatory power due to reliance on cross-sectional data.

Study	Topic	Y/N
Jeffery et al., 2006	FF near home/work & adult obesity	n
Williams et al., 2014	FF near schools & student obesity	y
Williams et al., 2015	FF near home & student obesity	y
Cobb et al, 2015	FF availability & child obesity (low-income)	y
Cooksey-Stowers, 2017	Food swamps & adult obesity	y
Turbutt et al., 2019	FF & student obesity	y
Jia et al., 2019	FF near home & obesity	y
Matsutzaki et al., 2020	FF near school & child obesity	y
Elbel et al., 2020	FF near home & child obesity	y

Table 1: empirical studies relating fast food and obesity using cross-sectional data

Notes: Y/N refers to whether the study did or did not find a significant relationship between fast food and obesity.

Many of these studies struggle to separate out the competing effects of confounding factors, such as socioeconomic deprivation, and fast food restaurants on obesity. The papers presented in Table 2 attempt to establish causality, finding a significant but small impact of FFOs on obesity, suggesting that they play a role in explaining rising childhood obesity within certain contexts.

Study	Topic	Y/N
Davis & Carpenter, 2009	FF near school & child obesity	y
Dunn, 2010	FF near home & adult obesity (urban women, non-white)	y
Currie et al., 2010	FF near school & child obesity (young teens and pregnant women)	y
Anderson & Matsa, 2011	FF consumption & adult obesity (offset other meals)	n
Dunn et al., 2012	FF near home & adult obesity (non-white, rural)	y
Alviola et al., 2014	FF near school & student obesity	y
Asirvatham et al., 2019	FF near school & student obesity	n
Han et al., 2020	FF near home & child obesity (public housing)	y
Dolton & Tafesse, 2022	FF near home & teen obesity	n
Libuy et al., 2023	FF near schools & student obesity	y

Table 2: empirical studies estimating the causal relationship between fast food and obesity

Notes: Y/N refers to whether the study did or did not find a significant correlation between fast food and obesity.

Of the studies that find a causal link, two stand out. Currie et al. (2010) find that the presence of a FFO within 0.1 miles of a US high school is associated with a 5.2% increase in its obesity rate, with the effect breaking down beyond that radius, consistent with high transportation costs for young teens. Caraher et al., (2016) find a similar spatial friction in their London case study, observing that FFOs more than 200 meters from school gates were less likely to be used at lunchtime. Libuy and co-authors (2023) conclude that a marginal

increase in FFOs within 800 meters of UK schools increases the incidence of overweight by 4.0% with respect to the sample mean (23.3%). They hypothesise that as students grow older and gain independence, they may purchase more FF on their school journey. These results, among others (Alviola et al., 2014; Cooksey-Stowers, 2017), create scope for banning FFOs near schools.

Economically, there is a strong argument for the government to intervene to reduce childhood obesity on the grounds of negative external effects and protecting the vulnerable. Obese individuals do not bear the full cost of their consumption and lifestyle decisions that contribute to their obesity, as the market fails to capture the social costs of their actions. Moral hazard, where individuals pay less attention to their diet or exercise because they have access to healthcare, leads to higher obesity rates and increases the costs of health and social care. The NHS spends £6.5bn every year treating obesity and related conditions, imposing an additional burden on the taxpayer and limiting other patients' access to care (Frontier Economics, 2022).

Frontier Economics also find the value of lost earnings due to obesity is significant. Obesity has a large negative impact on economic growth which stands to benefit the entire population, so the value of lost earnings (through premature mortality or lower productivity) has a significant social cost.

Younger individuals are more likely to overly discount the future and lack the self-control necessary to make rational consumption decisions. While parents play an important role in shaping how their children consume demerit goods, they can never fully influence them, introducing scope for the government to limit children's access to unhealthy foods.

Consumption habits established early in life are difficult to change, making obese children and adolescents around five times more likely to be obese in adulthood than their non-obese counterparts (Simmonds et al., 2015). In a 2014 report, Public Health England stresses the importance of making “the healthy choice the easy choice” by regulating the growth of FFOs. A number of councils have already taken steps to use planning policy to limit new FFOs by implementing exclusion zones around schools, yielding mixed results to date.

LAs only have power to ban new FFOs, so Brown et al. (2021) find no impact of the use of a school exclusion zone over three years on takeaways in Newcastle. In contrast, a study of an exclusion zone in Gateshead finds a 14% decrease in the proportion of FFOs to restaurants compared to similar LAs and a reduction in the density of FFOs by 12.45 per 100,000 people, reflecting an increase in non-FFOs, not a fall in FFOs (Brown et al., 2022). Whether this reform could have had an impact on obesity is unclear and requires further evidence.

The government should also consider alternatives to banning new FFOs near schools, as this reform is yet to be shown to be definitively effective and will come with practical implementation challenges. LAs may consider working with new and existing outlets to provide healthier, affordable food alternatives to ensure children do not go hungry when unable to access FF. They may also increase licensing costs for FFOs, internalising some of the costs associated with obesity. Restrictions on junk food advertising have been delayed by the government but are due to come in from 2025 (Ambrose, 2022). As a complementary solution, councils may also look to create/expand social spaces near schools that young teens can access for free.

Another alternative would be to commission a study to test the effectiveness of the exclusion zone in populations of interest – i.e., populations with high levels of obesity and deprivation. We create a natural experiment by identifying areas with populations of interest and randomly assign them to treatment and control groups (assuming a Randomised Control Trial or national-scale implementation is unfeasible). We could use propensity score matching to compare outcomes across LSOAs with similar levels of deprivation as Brown et al. (2022) do, as self-selection is not an issue. After five years of treatment, we use difference-in-difference to compare the trends in the control and treatment groups using longitudinal data that looks at FFOs and student obesity, assuming that both groups follow parallel trends in obesity rates prior to the cut-off period. A simplified regression specification is given by:

$$Obesity\ rate_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 Post_t + \beta_2 Treatment_i + \beta_3 (Post_t \times Treatment_i) + \gamma X_{it} + \epsilon_{it},$$

where β_3 gives the effect of the reform on obesity rates.

We do not expect there to be an immediate fall in the obesity rate after the introduction of the policy, so we imitate Cooper et al.'s (2011) modified difference-in-difference setup and estimate the effects of the policy from a break in the obesity rate time trend rather than comparing the levels of quality in the pre and post-policy periods. If the policy has a causal effect on obesity, then we will observe parallel trends in obesity rates across treatment and control groups pre-treatment and divergence post-treatment, with the size of the intervention effect given by the difference between E and D in Figure 1.

Figure 1: stylised difference-in-difference estimation

Q5 References

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